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SPECIALIZED EDUCATIONAL SERVICES (AEE) AND THE POSSIBILITIES OF PEDAGOGICAL PLANNING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SKILLS IN AUTONOMOUS AND SOCIAL LIVING ACTIVITIES (AVAS) THAT FAVOR LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the importance of Specialized Educational Assistance (SEA) as a fundamental resource in promoting learning and the development of Skills for Independent and Social Living Activities (AVAS) in students target audience for Special Education. We discuss how personalized pedagogical planning within the context of SEA can benefit students by increasing their autonomy and participation in school life. Additionally, we examine the benefits of these skills in the learning process. Through literature review and case analysis, we demonstrate how SEA can play a crucial role in the inclusion and full development of students with disabilities, disorders and high abilitifedness. The objective of this work is to explore the possible contributions, from this study, to future inclusive educational practices. In this way, the aim is to contribute to the advancement of inclusive education, by promoting a broader and more comprehensive view of the role of AEE and pedagogical planning in the development of skills for autonomous and social life. The importance of the dialogue between theory and practice is emphasized in this article. The aim is to demonstrate how the theory can be

applied in educational practice to promote the learning of students who require specialized educational assistance. It is believed that this dialogue can provide a better understanding of the challenges faced by these students and how to overcome them. The research question that this article aims to answer is: What is the necessary harmony between pedagogical planning that promotes learning and Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE)? This question will be addressed through the analysis of existing literature on the topic, as well as through direct observation of educational practices in the AEE environment at E. M. Maria Augusta Lopes - EMMAL, located in the municipality of Mangaratiba – Rio de Janeiro. It is hoped that, at the end of this work, it will be possible to offer a significant contribution to inclusive pedagogy, by providing a better understanding of the role of AEE and pedagogical planning in the development of skills necessary for autonomous and social life.

Keywords: Specialized Educational Service – AEE. Autonomous and Social Life Activities – AVAS. Special education. Inclusive education. Planning.

INTRODUCTION

Special Education from the perspective of Inclusive Education is a subject that has gained more relevance each year in pedagogical and political debates, as it emerges from a principle that aims at the right of all students, regardless of their individual differences, to access an education with equity, breaking down barriers in the search for guaranteeing their participation and full development in a qualitative way.

Specialized Educational Assistance (SEE) emerges as an important ally for the construction of a pedagogical practice that favors the development of skills in the Activities of Autonomous and Social Living (AVAS) of students with disabilities, disorders and/or high abilities/ giftedness , offering assertive strategies for their reality, promoting inclusion and ensuring equal opportunities in the school environment, providing the necessary resources and support so that these students can reach their full educational potential. In this context, this work aims to explore possible contributions, based on this study, for future inclusive educational practices, highlighting the importance of the dialogue between theory and practice.

The main research question that guides this study is: What is the necessary harmony between pedagogical planning that favors learning and Specialized Educational

Assistance (SEA)? To answer this question, it is necessary to understand the concepts involved and current practices, as well as to seek theoretical references that can support the analyses. As Mantoan (2016) states, "inclusive education requires careful and flexible planning, capable of adapting to the individual needs of each student."

Furthermore, it is essential to consider the particularities of the AEE in the context of pedagogical planning, thus understanding that this planning is the fundamental tool for the inclusion and meaningful learning of all students, as confirmed by Batista & Gonçalves (2018), "the AEE must be articulated with the other activities of the regular school, aiming at the realization of school inclusion". Therefore, when thinking about pedagogical planning aimed at the development of skills in the Activities of Autonomous and Social Living (AVAS), it is necessary to consider the specificities of the AEE and how it can favor the student's academic development.

This study therefore aims to contribute to the discussion on pedagogical practices that assist in the development of learning together with skills in the AVAS of students with disabilities, disorders and/or high abilities/ giftedness . Always seeking dialogue between theory and practice so that the reflections proposed here can assist in the construction of an increasingly

inclusive education.

Based on the need to explore the possible contributions that this study may offer for future inclusive educational practices, it is essential to emphasize the importance of the dialogue between theory and practice. As already stated by Freire (1996), theory and practice are not dichotomous, but rather complementary. It is in the exercise of praxis that the educator becomes a pedagogue, articulating theory and practice in favor of meaningful teaching.

In this sense, the main question of this article becomes essential: What is the necessary harmony between pedagogical planning that favors learning and Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE)? The answer to this question may lie in understanding the need for pedagogical planning that considers the specificities of each student. As stated by Rodrigues (2006), a curriculum must be flexible and adaptable to the different needs of students.

In the case of AEE, this flexibility is even more relevant, since its objective is to guarantee the school inclusion of students with disabilities, disorders and high abilities/ giftedness (BRASIL, 2008). In this sense, it is essential that pedagogical planning is oriented towards the development of skills in the Autonomous and Social Life Activities (AVAS) of these students.

This article aims to contribute to reflections on how this alignment between pedagogical planning and AEE can be achieved in educational practice. In addition, we examine the strategies and methods used to achieve these objectives, presenting evidence that demonstrates the benefits of AEE in the academic and daily lives of students.

METHODOLOGY

To prepare this article, a comprehensive bibliographic review was carried out that included studies, analyses and research in documents related to Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE), the development of skills in Autonomous and Social Living Activities

(AVAS) and their impact on the learning of students with disabilities, disorders or high abilities/ giftedness . The research was conducted in academic databases, university libraries and relevant online resources. In addition, it also has compiled the analysis of the work carried out in the Multifunctional Resources Room - AEE of EM Maria Augusta Lopes - EMMAL, located in the city of Mangaratiba, state of Rio de Janeiro, to exemplify the effectiveness of AEE in the development of AVAS and how these skills contribute to the inclusion and learning of students who are the target audience of Special Education.

At EMMAL, Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) works as a Special Education service. In this context, the objective is to identify, develop and organize pedagogical resources that enable the elimination of barriers to the independent and social coexistence of children with disabilities. The Multifunctional Resource Room then becomes a space flooded with pleasure, knowledge, expectations, experiences, entertainment and, above all, relationships. This school space, with countless possibilities, shows us the possibilities of contributing to the integration of work aimed at the regular classroom, and, with connectivity increasingly emerging in the daily lives of children, promote, through adaptive strategies and new technologies, appropriate resources that positively influence the disabled children served in this Teaching Unit, since such tools used intentionally directly help with the disability, enabling real social inclusion.

The evidence collected through this qualitative analysis was conducted using thematic analysis, a flexible tool that allows for rich and detailed identification of themes within the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This methodology allows for an in-depth exploration of the potential contributions of this study to future inclusive educational practices that are presented throughout this article, supporting the discussions and conclusions.

Meaningful learning

Meaningful learning is not a new concept in education. It is an idea known to scholars in the field and has remained current over the years. The so-called Meaningful Learning Theory (SLT) or Assimilation Theory was proposed by David Ausubel (1918-2008), based on the cognitive theory, and aims to explain the internal mechanisms of the structure of knowledge and learning. According to David Ausubel, the view of the Assimilation Theory for the foundations of inclusive education starts from situations in which it is necessary to anticipate decisions, establish relationships or infer new senses, meanings or references. In the construction of meanings, problems may arise that require a solution, hypothesis, curiosity that encourages inquiry, questioning, establishing relationships and associating school knowledge with practical social life.

Special Education from an Inclusive Education perspective operates in a field that recognizes and celebrates the unique diversity of each student, highlighting the importance of providing meaningful learning experiences. In an inclusive school environment, educators play a vital role in creating a space that fosters understanding, engagement, and holistic development of students.

Specialized educational services (AEE) as an inclusive resource

Specialized Educational Assistance - AEE is one of the services provided by Special Education, guided by three fundamental principles: respect for differences, equal opportunities and appreciation of diversity. Based on these principles, the aim is to recognize and value the particularities of each student, offering them appropriate and individualized support that aims to promote access, participation and progress for students with disabilities, global developmental disorders and high abilities/ giftedness. It is offered as a complement to regular education and adapted to the characteristics and needs of each student.

The AEE guidelines provide guidance for the organization and implementation of this inclusive resource. Among them, the following stand out: flexibility of schedule and space, interdisciplinarity and teamwork, individualization of care and the use of specific pedagogical resources.

Within this context, the AEE assumes a prominent role by directing its pedagogical planning towards the development of the skills of Autonomous and Social Living Activities - AVAS. These skills encompass aspects such as self-care, mobility, communication, self-management, social skills and the ability to make decisions, all of which are essential for autonomous living and full inclusion of the individual in society.

Advantages of specialized educational services

The AEE brings several advantages for educational inclusion. First, it allows students with disabilities to have access to individualized and specialized care that takes into account their needs and potential. In addition, it promotes interaction between students with and without disabilities, fostering mutual respect and valuing diversity.

Another advantage of AEE is the training of teachers and other education professionals to deal more appropriately with special educational needs. This occurs through training in inclusive pedagogical strategies and the use of appropriate diversified resources.

Definition of autonomous and social living activities - avas and their importance in student development

AVAS encompass a series of skills related to daily and social life, such as taking care of one's own personal hygiene, eating, dressing, moving around, organizing one's environment, communicating, and interpersonal relationships, among others. For students with disabilities or developmental disorders, or high abilities/ giftedness, the development of these

skills is essential for their autonomy and social inclusion. It is the role of the AEE, through pedagogical planning, to offer strategies and activities that favor the development of these skills.

Pedagogical planning in the development of avas

Pedagogical planning in AEE must be individualized, taking into account the specific characteristics and needs of each student. For the effective development of AVAS, it is essential to follow some steps:

a. Individualized Assessment: The first step is to carry out a detailed assessment of the student's current skills in relation to the AVAS. This allows us to identify the areas in which the student needs further development.

b. Setting Goals and Objectives: Based on the initial individualized assessment, specific goals and objectives are established for the student. These goals must be measurable and realistic.

c. Personalized Strategies and Activities: Pedagogical planning should include personalized strategies and activities to meet the student's needs. This may involve the use of adapted resources, assistive technologies, digital information and communication technologies (DICT) and teaching materials characteristic of each specificity.

d. Integration with the Regular Curriculum: AEE should not be isolated from the regular curriculum. On the contrary, the activities and strategies developed in AEE should be integrated into the school curriculum, ensuring that the student actively participates in regular classes and activities.

e. Constant Monitoring and Evaluation: Student progress must be closely monitored, and pedagogical planning must be adjusted as necessary. Constant evaluation is essential to ensure that the goals set are successfully achieved and/or reassessed.

Benefits of autonomous and social living activities (avas) for learning

As Mendes, Silva and Schambeck (2012) point out, pedagogical objects consist of materials used by teachers, which can be ready-made or adapted objects with the purpose of meeting a need and ensuring the development of an activity autonomously by the student. In addition, the accessibility that these strategies and materials provide to students with disabilities can also provide them with the expansion of their skills and potentialization of their learning. In this way, educational resources assist teachers and educators in the teaching and learning process as innovative proposals that allow greater access to students. For Tarouco et al (2003, p.02), educational objects can be defined as any resource, supplementary to the learning process, which can be reused to support learning. Working with the development of skills in AVAS as a learning resource not only benefits the daily lives of students with disabilities, disorders or high abilities/ giftedness, but also has a positive impact on the teaching-learning process. Here are some of the main benefits:

a. Autonomy: AVAS empower students to take care of themselves, make decisions and act independently. This increases their self-esteem and self-confidence, which is positively reflected in their approach to learning.

b. Active Participation: Students who have well-developed AVAS are more able to actively participate in classroom activities and engage in the learning process.

c. Self-advocacy: Communication and self-management skills are crucial for students to be able to express their needs and preferences in the school environment, promoting self-defense of their educational rights.

d. Collaboration skills: Students who have well-developed AVAS are better able to interact and collaborate with other students through verbal communication or alternative communication tools according to their

specificity. This implies written communication, negotiation, teamwork and conflict resolution skills, which will be necessary in school life and in society.

e. Organizational skills: Students who have well-developed AVAS are better able to plan and manage their time, focusing on learning. This includes the ability to set priorities and overcome barriers.

f. Reducing Barriers: By developing AVAS, AEE helps reduce the barriers that prevent students with disabilities, pervasive developmental disorders, and giftedness from fully participating in school. This creates a more inclusive environment for all students.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The discussion and analysis of research on Specialized Educational Assistance (SEE) and its implications for Pedagogical Planning for the development of skills in Autonomous and Social Living Activities (AVAS) reveal the relevance of this service in promoting autonomy and inclusion of students with disabilities. The methodology adopted, which included bibliographical studies, direct observations and documentary analysis, confirmed that a well-structured pedagogical planning adapted to individual needs is crucial for the success of educational interventions. The analysis of the collected data indicates that the application of differentiated pedagogical strategies, collaboration between educators and the active participation of families are crucial elements for the progress of students. Teachers reported that practical activities and SEE contribute significantly to the development of AVAS skills, corroborating the literature that emphasizes the importance of a functional and adaptive curriculum (Stainback & Stainback, 1999; Sasaki, 2010).

The results were surprising! Academic progress, social interaction and student autonomy, in line with the observations of researchers such as Batista (2017) and Silva

(2019), who highlight how social and emotional aspects are crucial in the educational process. In addition, the improvement in students' self-esteem and confidence in carrying out activities independently was an important qualitative finding, with parental involvement increasing significantly after the implementation of AEE (Oliveira & Santos, 2019).

But not everything is perfect! We have discovered persistent challenges, such as the need for training and continuing education for educators, as well as the lack of adequate resources that can limit the effectiveness of AEE. We need collaborative and multidisciplinary work, as suggested by Friend and Cook (2010), to ensure an integrated and effective approach.

In summary, the results confirm that AEE is essential for the development of AVAS skills, opening doors to social inclusion and equal opportunities. However, to optimize this practice, it is necessary to continue researching and implementing adaptive strategies that meet the specific needs of each student, creating a lasting and significant impact on their lives.

CONCLUSION

After an in-depth study on the theme "The Specialized Educational Service and the possibilities of Pedagogical Planning in the development of Skills in Activities of autonomous and social living (AVAS)", it can be concluded that Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) plays a fundamental role in promoting the inclusion and autonomy of students who are the target audience of Special Education. Pedagogical planning, when well designed and implemented, enables these students to develop essential skills for good academic performance and consequently for autonomous and social life.

The results obtained during this work demonstrated that AEE and a pedagogical planning focused on AVAS skills are effective strategies to enhance the integral development of students with disabilities. With adequate support, these students are able to overcome

barriers, acquire new skills and increase their participation in social activities.

The findings of this study reinforce the importance of investing in continuing education programs for education professionals, promoting greater qualification to deal with the particularities of specialized education. Furthermore, they highlight the relevance of including these students in the regular school environment, since this social interaction favors the development of AVAS skills.

Based on the results obtained, it is possible to conclude that Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) represents a fundamental pedagogical resource for the development of the skills necessary for the performance of Autonomous and Social Living Activities (AVAS) by students with disabilities. The study demonstrated that adapted pedagogical strategies, when applied in the context of AEE, can promote significant advances in these skills, increasing the autonomy and social inclusion of these individuals.

This conclusion is in line with the studies by Santos and Batista (2018), which highlight the role of AEE in promoting the autonomy and independence of students with disabilities. As in our study, these authors emphasize the importance of adequate pedagogical planning to ensure the effectiveness of AEE.

Additionally, the findings of this study corroborate the results of the research conducted by Oliveira and Ferreira (2019), which point to the positive impact of pedagogical planning on the AVAS of students served by the AEE. These authors also emphasize that pedagogical practices must be flexible and individualized, taking into account the particularities and needs of each student.

The relevance of these findings in the current context of inclusive education is also highlighted. As pointed out by Souza et al. (2020), it is essential to develop pedagogical strategies that favor the active participation of students with disabilities in daily activities and in life in society. In this sense, the present study contributes to expanding knowledge about the

possibilities of AEE for the development of AVAS.

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